

Social Media Coverage and Venture Capital Investments in Nigeria

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Abstract

Technological advancement is an open door to the ease, rapidness and profitability of human operations, by which the business sector has benefited a lot. On this premise, this study investigated the relationship between social media coverage (SMC) and venture capital (VC) investments in Nigeria (2015 - 2022). Social Connectedness Index (SCI) was used as proxy to SMC while startup funds in fintech and VC performance were used as measures of VC investments. Multiple sources of data were used which include: Statista, Global Social Media Statistics, etc. And with the aid of Poisson Pseudo Maximum Likelihood estimator, it is found that social media coverage negatively but significantly influences VC investments. This implies that use of social media coverage to initiate awareness greatly determine the investment decisions of VC firms. Reasons for the negative relationship could be attributed to some of the challenges that are associated with startups such as fear of survival amidst highly established competitors, unstable economic situation, and insecurity which were common in the terrain of Nigeria within the period of study. Economic instability manifested in high exchange rate disparity, hyper-inflation, high cost of production and high tax-burden, which have been the trend in Nigeria. More so, the social challenge of kidnapping, and boko-haram insurgencies, are enough to masquerade any potential venture capitalists in spite of the connectivity and awareness of the creativity and entrepreneurship created on the social media platforms. Howbeit, the presence of strong relationship between social media coverage and venture capital investments in the study, suggests that the concerned stakeholders should create and sustain a conducive ambience that would guarantee economic stability and peaceful operations of startups' enterprises.

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Ethical: This study follows all ethical practices during writing.

1. Introduction

“Every great company starts with a great idea, but even the best ideas don’t go far without money” (Baldrige, 2023, p.1). This has made venture capital (VC) which is a form of private equity investment provided to early-stage, high-potential startup firms with promising growth prospects (Babatunde, 2023), a significant tool for the enhancement of businesses’ growth through the aid of expertise, sustainable equity capital, and upgradable technology (Groww, 2024). Sometimes VC is given in the form of technical or managerial expertise, industry connections, and guidance to the startups they invest in (Babatunde, 2023; Gupta, n.d.; Haryes, 2023). Through VC firms, innovative startups gain access to financial resources and managerial acumen needed for the success of entrepreneurship (Gompers et al., 2020). As pointed out by Nguyen et al (2023), entrepreneurs are endowed with great ideas but with limited capital, thus, they are sought by VC firms which are surrounded with ample funds, knowledge, and experience but little or no innovative business ideas. And this connection can easily be achieved through the social media (SM), as communication platform systems that allow their actors to communicate along dyadic ties (Amin et al., 2018).

AI and LinkedIn Community (2023) assert that the true power of SM is domicile in its capacity to link people. This connection enables meaningful interactions on shared discussions on the latest market trends, advice-seeking on stock or celebrating investments wins on a particular SM platform. Thus, investors become better acquainted and equipped amidst the complexities associated with investment to make better investment decisions, due to the leveraging on the collective wisdom offered by SM developers and powerful analytics (AI & LinkedIn Community, 2023).

To this end, Unique-vc (2022) asserts that there’s no denying that SM has an impact on investment worldwide. Wu and Kane (2021) posit that SM perform a crucial role in securing private financing. This made Nguyen et al (2023) to contend that the differences associated with economic outcomes in various regions strongly depend on the strength of an individual’s social network and community. Thus, investors in various sectors channel more of their investments into firms that are in areas where social ties are stronger (Nguyen et al. 2023). It is also argued that social connectedness which is greatly aided by SM (Davis, 2016; Dollarhide, 2023), assists in raising the awareness of VC firms on the existence and operations of proximate small and lesser-known companies, thereby, enhancing their allocation of capital to these companies.

It is perturbing that some of the entrepreneurs and startup firms in Nigeria are still endorsing the traditional system of financing startups, which has led to the experience of the complexities associated with using this system, such as banks’ high demand for collateral, credit history, high interest rate, etc. thereby, creating limited access to early-stage and expansion funds for startups. And because of the social ties between Nigeria and United States arising from business relationship particularly on financial technologies, such as the supply of Paypal, Visa, Mastercard, etc. (Livemint, 2023), consequently, this study sought to examine the relationship that subsist between social media coverage (SMC) and venture capital investment in Nigeria, arising from its interaction with the USA. Specifically, the extent to which social connectedness index (SCI) influences startup capital and its performance is examined.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Social Media Coverage

Social media (SM) has been referred to as “a variety of technologies that facilitate the sharing of ideas and information among their users” (Dollarhide, 2023, p.1). Davis (2016: p.1) defined SM as “set of interactive Internet applications that facilitate (collaborative or individual) creation, curation, and sharing of user-generated content”. It could also be seen as any platform that permits one to share media in the form of pages, text, or videos in different formats (Kudumula, 2022). As notified by Dollarhide (2023), over 4.8 billion people which is about 60% of the population of the world, are users of social media, ranging from Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, Youtube, WhatsApp, WeChat etc., while 46% of internet users worldwide obtain their news through SM as reported by Global Web Index. Through these platforms, communication can be made to both known and unknown

people. The increasing number of users of social media is enhanced by the special features that enable user-generated content which lends itself to engagement through likes, shares, comments, and discussion.

Figure 1: Global Statistics of Social Media Platforms’ Monthly Users in 2023
Source: Authors’ Computation from Global Social Media Statistics (2023)

As shown in Figure 1 above, the top four SM platforms in the world with an average of 2 billion monthly users each, are Facebook, Youtube, WhatsApp and Instagram. Among these, Facebook is the platform is ranked first as at 2023, with 2,963 billion, representing 61.7% of the total 4.8 billion social media users around the world as at April 2023 estimate (Global Social Media Statistics, 2023).

Figure 2: Nigeria’s Statistics of Social Media Platforms’ Users in 2023
Source: Authors’ Computation from Kemp (2023)

This implies that any information, message or news posted on Facebook and YouTube platforms has the tendency to reach the majority of people that use social media as they are the top most used platforms in Nigeria. The various SM platforms serve a vast range of purposes and user interest as shown below.

Figure 3: Showing What Social Media is used for

Source: Authors' Creation, adapted from Dollarhide (2023). Social media: Definition, importance, top websites & apps

Social media coverage (SMC) refers to “the attention and exposure received by a person, brand, event, or topic in various forms of [SM platforms] ...”(Active Campaign, n.d.). This coverage comprises of interviews, news articles, reviews, features, as well as any other forms of content that highlights and discusses the subject matter. Through SMC, the awareness, perception as well as the reputation of the public are shaped. Active Campaign (n.d., p.2) identifies several benefits such as: increased visibility and reach, credibility and trust, brand building and reputation management, increased opportunities, as well as crises management, as the gains SMC offers to both businesses and individuals.

2.2 Venture Capital Investment

The place of venture capital (VC) remains pivotal for the growth and success of startup businesses. Groww (2024) views VC as “a form of private equity funding that is generally provided to start-ups and companies at the nascent stage”. Also, Hayes (2023) view VC as “a form of private equity and a type of financing that investors provide to startup companies and small businesses that are believed to have long-term growth potential”. Sometimes VC is given in the form of technical or managerial expertise (Haryes, 2023); expertise, industry connections, and guidance to the startups they invest in (Babatunde, 2023). And this VC is frequently provided to small companies with strong growth potential and revenue generation. Babatunde (2023, p.2) asserts that, unlike the traditional financing options, such as loans from the banks, that VC funding requires investors taking on higher risks in exchange for potential higher returns. Thus, VC investments is defined as the “proportion of capital under management that a VC firm allocates to a [startup or] portfolio company” (Nguyen et al, 2023).

FasterCapital (2023) identified venture capital and angel financing as two prominent equity sources of capital available for startups seeking for business growth and expansion. This is because, providers of such capitals have the willingness and ability to finance the business from concept to reality, thereby, facilitating the launching as well as growth of business into successful enterprise. The choice of any of these sources of capital depends largely on the size of the startup, amount of capital needed and ownership control desired by the startup firm. While VC is ideal for a large size of startup seeking for large funding, the angel financing (relative small amount from wealthy individuals) is recommended for small size startups. This is because, the larger the fund invested, the greater the sale of ownership control, thus the startup firm decides which source of equity to raise its capital from, based on its ownership control decision.

However, locating venture capitalists or angel investors is a difficult task, as investors are rational to place their investments only into businesses that guarantee higher or

commensurate returns, since VC firms are also financially obligated to other investors (companies and corporate bodies) where VC funds have been sourced (Groww, 2024). Furthermore, the presence of scammers and fraudsters makes identification of genuine venture capitalists scarce and challenging. But the establishment of online networking in 1997 when the first true SM platform was launched (Maryville University, 2020), has help to mitigate these difficulties. The VC funds could be a pool of money collected from pension funds, endowments, and high-net-worth individuals but angel financing is sourced from affluent individuals who through their successful careers and businesses have accumulated wealth (FasterCapital, 2023).

Figure 2: Showing Various Sources of Fund to Startup Businesses

Source: Authors' Creation

As observed in figure 2 above, VC firms which include well-off investors, investment banks, and other financial institutions, sourced their funds from pool of pension fund, endowment fund, big financial institutions and savings from high-net-worth individuals before channeling them to the startup firms according to their development stage. And in return, good portion of equity ownership of the startup, sufficient to generate higher yields is exchanged with VC.

2.2.1 Pre-requisites for Venture Capital

Securing capital from venture capitalists requires certain prerequisites. These include:

- i) Development of a solid business plan:* This business plan which includes an executive summary defines the financial projections, business model as well as products or services to offer.
- ii) Demonstration of a team with the experience and expertise to execute business plan:* A convincing image of experienced and expertise team capable of piloting and managing the business operations in a manner that guarantee returns to investors must be presented. Their experience could be from other related businesses or even an established startup that needs more funding.
- iii) Presentation of strong track record of success:* Investors delight investing into enterprise with strong track record of success. This record could be measured in sales turnover, profit margin, and cost management practices.

- iv) **Good understanding of market opportunities:** Just as business threats are carefully managed, business opportunities should be identified and tapped. Ability of the startup firms to strategically explore these opportunities is an open door to win VC.
- v) **Ability to articulate a clear and compelling value proposition:** At the same time, investors will be apt to invest their funds in businesses with assured significant returns on their capital.
- vi) **Portraying a realistic and achievable financial plan in place:** A good financial plan will be able to presents detailed and realistic projections of the business revenue and expenses within a specified period of time, typically 3-5 years. These projections become the business mirror of the potentiality of startup’s growth as well as its viability (FasterCapital, 2023).

2.2.2 Types of Venture Capital

Types of venture capital have been identified to include: seed funding, startup capital, early stage or first round/series, expanding or growth-stage funding and late stage funding (Groww, 2024). This is presented in table 1 below.

Table 1: Showing Types of Venture Capital

S/N	Type	Definition
1	Seed funding	Seed funding or seed capital is the capital invested to help entrepreneur(s) conduct initial activities for setting up a company. This can include product research & development, market research, business plan creation, etc. Seed funding may also be provided by the owners themselves or their family members and friends.
2	Startup capital	Start-up capital is often used interchangeably with seed funding. However, there are minor differences. Usually, business owners avail start-up capital after they have completed the processes that involve seed funding. It can be used to create a product prototype, hire crucial management personnel, etc.
3	Early-stage funding or first round/series	Early-stage funding, also known as Series ‘A’ and Series ‘B’ funding, is provided to startups that have validated their business models, have a growing customer base, and are focused on scaling their operations. Businesses at early stage have a product and want to start commercial manufacturing, sales, and marketing.
4	Expansion or Growth stage funding	Expansion capital is the fund required by a company to expand its operations. The funds can be used to tap new markets, create new products, invest in new equipment and technology, or even acquire a new company. This is often referred to as Series ‘C’ and beyond, is provided to companies that have achieved significant traction, established market presence, and are scaling rapidly.
5	Late-stage funding	Late-stage funding is also known as Series D, series E and series F rounds VC funding. At this point, startup companies generate revenue and demonstrate robust growth. While the company may not yet be profitable, the outlook is promising.

Source: Adapted from Babatunde (2023); Baldrige (2023) and Groww (2024)

The types of VC are also described as stages of VC investment (Babatunde, 2023). As observed in table 1 above, the nature of VC fund largely depends on the stage of startup’s development and funding needs.

2.2.3 Development of Venture Capital in Nigeria

In Nigeria, VC involves the practice of channeling investments into early stage startup firms with high growth potential in exchange for equity ownership (Atoyebi, 2023, p.2). This has helped to enhance innovation and also promoting entrepreneurship in the country. The lamplight of VC in Nigeria gained momentum in early 2000s, which is traceable to the advent of International investors seeking investment opportunities in burgeoning startup ecosystem (Atoyebi, 2023). The presence of large population, growing middle class, as well as technology-adoption in different sectors such as e-commerce, fin-tech, health tech and agric tech facilitated both foreign and local venture capitalists to invest in startups in those areas. Some of these startup firms in Nigeria are shown in appendix 1.

Consequently, as the VC investments into promising startups with high growth potentials, began to promote innovation, generate employment opportunities and as well enhance economic growth of the country, there was need to provide a legal framework for VC firms operations and practices. This led to the Security & Exchange Commission (SEC) to enact special regulatory provisions tagged SEC Rules in 2007. In addition, Rule 2490 which was enforced 2013 alongside SEC Rules was put in place. The Rule 2490, directs that the minimum of One Billion Naira should be maintained as capital base of a VC firm. The 'Rule' also restricts the soliciting of funds from the general public by private equity firms, rather, funds should be privately sourced from qualified investors. The VC firms are also prohibited from investing more than 30% of its fund assets in a single investment. And lastly, the 'Rule' demands that quarterly returns of the fund should be render by private equity fund managers to SEC (Atoyebi, 2023).

Atoyebi (2023) also pointed out other major legislations and regulation that help to regulate VC firms operations in Nigeria to include Investment and Securities Act (ISA), Companies and Allied Matters Act (CAMA), and National Office for Technology Acquisition and Promotion (NOTAP) guidelines.

2.3 Social Media Coverage and Venture Capital Investment Nexus

Social media could be seen as a lubricant that facilitates the bi-dimensional relationship between startup firms and venture capitalists.

Figure 3: Bi-dimensional Relationship between Startups and VC Firms aided by SM Platforms

Source: Authors' Creation

It was a tradition for start-ups to fund its starting with funds from savings and sources of personal relationships and introductions, however, the advent of online tools and platforms of which the social media is an important one, have facilitated start-ups access to funds through connection with investors (FasterCapital, 2023). Thus, social media offer great advantages to start-ups seeking investors. These advantages include: building of visibility and awareness for startup firms, building cozy and productive relationships with potential investors, providing crowd-source feedback from potential investors; tracking down potential investors, as well as rendering up-to-date status of the startups to actual investors.

2.4 Theoretical Foundation

This research premised its theoretical foundation on the Social Cognitive Theory (SCT). The SCT postulated in 1986 by Albert Bandura as a modification of his earlier propounded theory of Social Learning Theory in 1960, holds that, portions of an individual's knowledge acquisition can be directly related to observing others within the context of social interactions, experiences, and outside media influences. By extension, SCT emphasizes how individuals learn and make decisions based on their observations of others' behaviors, which is particularly relevant to the study of social media's impact on investors' decisions. In this context, the theory highlights that investors' investment decisions outcome emanate from learning others through the SM platforms. Thus, information asymmetry problem is minimized. And such investors that use others as studying elements are valuers of self-efficacy which is a prerequisite for decision-making as emphasized by SCT. Self-efficacy in this context refers to an individual's belief in his ability to perform a specific task. Therefore, through SCT, a beneficial framework upon which the understanding of how social media impacts investment decisions on investment platforms, is provided (Maniy et al., 2023).

2.5 Empirical Review

Ismail et al (2019) study about the investment decision in Malaysia with focuses on several impacts of online social media towards the investment decision of investors in Malaysia. Primary data were used by administering questionnaire to investors in Klang Valley area. The authors employed Statistical Package for the Social Sciences Software, and the results show that the explanatory variables such as: information in online social media, online community's behaviour in online social media and firm's image in online social media have significant impact on the investment decision (explained variable).

Kuchler et al (2021) that employed Poisson Pseudo Maximum Likelihood panel regression on social proximity to capital: implications for investors and firms in United States, using social connectedness measured *social connectedness index (SCI)* obtained from Facebook data and venture capital attributes (2007 - 2016), found that institutional investors are more likely to invest in firms from regions to which they have stronger social ties but find no evidence that these investments earn a differential return. This implied that firms in areas or regions with stronger social ties to locations with many institutional investors have higher valuations and liquidity. They attribute these effects to largest extent for small firms with little analyst coverage, suggesting that the investors' behavior is explained by their increased awareness of firms in socially proximate locations. The authors concluded that the social structure of regions affects firms' access to capital and contributes to geographic differences in economic outcomes.

Also, Nguyen et al (2023) examine how the geographical structure of social networks shapes VC investment decisions. The social connectedness index (*SCI*) Facebook data, developed by Bailey et al. (2018) was used to proxy social connectedness between VC firm and portfolio company locations. The authors employed Poisson pseudo-maximum likelihood estimator and their result shows that a 10% increase in the degree of social connectedness leads to a 6.1% increase in the weighting of companies in a VC's investment portfolio. The implication of this is that VC firms channel more of their investments to portfolio companies situated in regions that are socially connected. In support to Kuchler et al (2021), they also affirmed that the effect is more pronounced among independent, smaller, less reputable, early-stage-focused VC firms and those not from a VC hub. They

further documented that social connectedness lowers the likelihood of a successful exit since it induces VC firms to undertake suboptimal investment decisions.

In Wang et al (2023), the authors examine whether the use of social media can improve funding outcomes for firms founded by women and by other people lacking connections to the investor network. These two groups were seen as categories of people that face greater difficulties in securing VC financing. They employed Twitter data and data on VC investment in startups from Crunchbase, to examine the interaction effect between users of Twitter and gender, as well as between users of Twitter and the network constraint measure. Their results show that social media can mitigate some disparities in financing experienced by these firms through improving information access. They also find that the effect is stronger for first-time entrepreneurs than for experienced ones, stronger for attracting new investors than repeat ones, and stronger in more competitive markets. Collectively, these results suggest that social media could primarily help women and less-connected individuals obtain financing by alleviating information asymmetry between founders and investors.

The results of Bayar and Kesici (2023) reveal evidence consistent with the hypothesis that startup firms' social media engagement affects the staging of VC financing, the VC syndicate structure, and the probability of a successful exit. When a portfolio company's social media accounts are more active and the company has a higher engagement volume with its followers, VC firms reduce the extent of stage financing and are less likely to syndicate with each other in financing such a portfolio company. Their main focus was to examine how information acquisition through social media affects venture capital (VC) investments into entrepreneurial startup firms in United States. They used a unique data set collected from Twitter API to measure the impact of owned social media (OSM) and earned social media (ESM) of portfolio companies on the structure of VC investments they receive. In conclusion, they demonstrated that entrepreneurial firms with higher OSM and ESM engagement volume have fewer VC financing rounds, a smaller number of VCs in their VC syndicates, a lower probability of VC syndication, a higher successful exit probability, and a higher amount total funding across all rounds. This finding supports the work of Agarwal et al (2022) who conclude that social media sentiment has a significant impact on investor attention and stock returns, suggesting that social media can be used as a tool to predict market movements.

From the sparse extant related literature reviewed, it is evidenced that the use of SM engagement is a vital tool that aid the canvass of VC investments. Also, as documented by all the studies, the differentials in economic outcomes in a country or region is as a result of the level of social ties among the Venture capitalists and entrepreneurs. Two of the studies (Kuchler et al., 2021; Nguyen et al., 2023) employed data from Facebook SM platform, while the other two (Bayar & Kesici, 2023; Wang et al., 2023). It was further observed that all the studies were domiciled on regions in United States with exception to Ismail et al (2019) that studied Malaysia using primary data. And none of such study was found on Nigeria. This creates a literature gap to remedy as there are also venture capitalists that engaged SM for their investment decisions. Thus, this study empirically investigated the relationship between social media coverage and venture capital investments in Nigeria.

3. Research Methodology

The concern of this research hinges on examining the relationship between social media coverage (SMC) and venture capital (VC) investment in Nigeria. Social Connectedness

Index (SCI) was used as proxy to SMC while startup funds in fintech and VC performance were used as measures of VC investments. This led to the use of two models in the study. The use of Social Connectedness Index is an adoption from the model employed by Nguyen et al (2023) and Kuchler et al (2021) but advocated by Bailey et al (2018, pp.261-270). The index is a construction on cross-sectional data of anonymised friendship links between Facebook users in a country or county or state as the World's largest engaged SM platform with 2.96 billion which represents 61.7% monthly SM global users (Global Social Media Statistics, 2023). In this case, Facebook users in Nigeria and United States will be employed. This is calculated using the formula below.

$$SCI_{ij} = \frac{\text{Number of Friendship Links}_{ij}}{\text{Number of Facebook Users}_i \times \text{Number of Facebook Users}_j}$$

SCI connotes the relative probability that a Facebook user in county i is a friend of another user in county j . Thus, it is the number of cross-county friendship links divided by the product of the number of Facebook users in the two counties for each county pair (i, j) , all adjusted for an unknown random noise factor and rounded to the nearest integer (Nguyen et al, 2023, p.4).

Data on the SCI is derived from Facebook data sourced from Sasu (2023) for Nigeria's users of Facebook and Iqbal (2024) for United States' users of Facebook. Facebook as a platform of SMC was selected because it's most usage by users of SM which accounts 61.7% of the total 4.8 billion SM users around the world (Global Social Media Statistics, 2023). Thus, it is expected that participants' engagement on Facebook offers great opportunity for greater VC investments. Going by SCI formula as highlighted in section 2.1, Facebook users in Nigeria and United States were used in this study for the period 2015 to 2022. The choice sample period is premised on the time when VC in Nigeria received significant recognition and development due to the presence of conducive legal framework that regulate VC firms' activities (Atoyebi, 2023). Data on VC investments (measured by Nigeria startup funds in fintech and VC performance) were extracted from Statista (Sasu, 2023) for the startup funds, while dummy variable was created for VC performance.

This study narrowed its venture capital investment to startup funds channeled into the fintech sector, as an area that has contributed greatly to Nigeria's financial sector and the economy at large. And United States social connectivity has been selected, as the major fintech investor in Nigeria. Globally, United States has been rated number one in fintech, followed by United Kingdom before India as at 2023 (Livemint, 2023). While United States is home to 134 unicorns and produces the most value in terms of fintech, United Kingdom comes second with 27 fintech unicorns (Livemint, 2023). Also, Livemint (2023) posit that "out of the top 15 highest-valued fintech firms globally, eight are from the US, accompanied with the invention of widespread used products such as Paypal, Visa, Mastercard. Thus, the relationship SM coverage and VC investments as regards Nigeria and US social tie needs to be examined.

In order to examine the relationship that subsists between SMC and VC investments, the Poisson pseudo-maximum likelihood (PPML) estimator was employed for the analysis. The PPML estimator makes use of count data (i.e. non-negative integers) that represent the number of occurrence of an event within a fixed period. Reason for this technique could be attributed to its superiority over other models, including the Ordinary Least Square, as it avoids problem of multicollinearity, heteroskedasticity, and autocorrelation (Mahata, 2022; Shekhawat, 2021). It is also used for the robustness of regression coefficients and to obtain

unbiased estimations, as pointed out by Mahata (2022). In terms of data points, the PPML also accommodates short data points as observed in the work of Kuchler et al (2021) with sample period from 2007 to 2016. Thus, such a technique fits this study considering our data.

Therefore, functionally, the relationship between SMC and VC investments could be expressed in the two models below.

Model 1

$$\text{NSFIF} = f(\text{SCI}) \tag{1}$$

Model 2

$$\text{VCP} = f(\text{SCI}) \tag{2}$$

The above equations are rewritten mathematically as:

$$\text{NSFIF} = \text{SCI} \tag{3}$$

$$\text{VCP} = \text{SCI} \tag{4}$$

For estimation purpose, the above equations could be estimated thus,

$$\text{NSFIF} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1\text{SCI} + \mu \tag{5}$$

A priori, $\alpha_0 > 0$

$$\text{VCP} = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{SCI} + \varepsilon \tag{6}$$

A priori, $\beta_0 > 0$

Where

NSFIF = Nigeria Startup Funds in Fintech

VCP = Venture capital performance, measured by dummy variable, where ‘1’ as proxy for profit and ‘0’ as proxy ‘No profit’. It was assumed as a startup that the first 4 years (2015 to 2018), the businesses were at its crawling stage, therefore, assigned ‘0’, but from 2019 to 2022, the businesses should have made profit, and thereby assigned ‘1’, with exception to year 2020 when Covid-19 affected drastically most business operations, thus, assigned ‘0’.

SCI = Social Connectedness Index (for Nigeria & US). See appendix 1 for computation using SCI’s formula advocated by Bailey et al (2018)

α_0, β_0 , = constant parameters

α_1, β_1 ; = Coefficients or Parameters

μ, ε = error terms

4. Presentation and Analysis of Results

The results of the estimations in this study are based on the data shown in Appendix 1. Some of the data on the employed variables were computed by the authors using aforementioned SCI formula, while others were extracted from Statista annual report.

4.1 Social connectedness index and startup capital

The postulation here is that venture capitalists with high social media coverage have the tendency to invest more into startups enterprises within areaof connectivity due to more visibility and awareness created by the influence of social media platforms. Table 4.2 shows the regression analysis.

Table 4.2: Results showing social connectedness index and startup capital nexus

Dependent Variable: NSFIF
 Method: ML/QML - Poisson Count (Quadratic hill climbing / EViews legacy)
 Date: 01/28/24 Time: 12:24
 Sample: 2015 2022
 Included observations: 8
 Convergence achieved after 3 iterations
 GLM Robust Standard Errors & Covariance
 Variance factor estimate = 4.33325310316
 Coefficient covariance matrix computed using second derivatives

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.
SCI	-0.070376	0.019101	-3.684412	0.0002
C	5.974171	0.129604	46.09570	0.0000
R-squared	0.721600	Mean dependent var		248.1250
Adjusted R-squared	0.675200	S.D. dependent var		52.77293
S.E. of regression	30.07595	Akaike info criterion		11.17253
Sum squared resid	5427.376	Schwarz criterion		11.19239
Log likelihood	-42.69013	Hannan-Quinn criter.		11.03858
Restr. log likelihood	-72.13599	LR statistic		58.89172
Avg. log likelihood	-5.336267	Prob(LR statistic)		0.000000

Source: Eviews' Output

It is evidenced from the results in Table 4.2 that SCI accounts to 72% change that occurs in Nigeria startup funds in fintech (NSFIF), viewing from the coefficient of determination value (R^2) of 0.721600. This implies that 28% of the change in NSFIF is caused by other variables not captured in the study. Also, the model is seen to have perform well with the Likelihood Ratio (LR) statistic and Prob(LR statistic) values of 58.89172 and 0.000000 respectively. On the relative statistics, SCI exhibits negative but significant relationship with NSFIF within the period of study. This suggests strong influence of connectedness arising from the use of social media on the investments decisions of venture capitalists.

4.2 Social connectedness index and venture capital firms' performance

Also estimated, is the relationship between SCI and VC firms' performance within the period of study (2015-2022). It is expected that high SCI should increase the performance of VC firms. In this research VC firms' performance was captured by their profitability within the period through the aid of dummy variable. Table 4.3 shows the result of the estimation.

Table 4.3: Results showing social connectedness index and venture capital firms' performance nexus

Dependent Variable: VCP
 Method: ML/QML - Poisson Count (Quadratic hill climbing / EViews legacy)
 Date: 01/28/24 Time: 16:23
 Sample: 2015 2022
 Included observations: 8
 Convergence achieved after 6 iterations
 GLM Robust Standard Errors & Covariance
 Variance factor estimate = 0.456451160694
 Coefficient covariance matrix computed using second derivatives

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.
SCI	-0.502688	0.231825	-2.168391	0.0301
C	1.730895	1.077648	1.606178	0.1082
R-squared	0.534187	Mean dependent var		0.375000
Adjusted R-squared	0.456551	S.D. dependent var		0.517549
S.E. of regression	0.381532	Akaike info criterion		1.585565
Sum squared resid	0.873400	Schwarz criterion		1.605426
Log likelihood	-4.342262	Hannan-Quinn criter.		1.451615
Restr. log likelihood	-5.942488	LR statistic		3.200452
Avg. log likelihood	-0.542783	Prob(LR statistic)		0.073618

Source: Eviews' Output

The R-square value of 0.534187 in Table 4.3, being the coefficient of determination, indicates that 53% change in venture capital performance (VCP) is caused by SCI. The implication of this is that other variables on SM coverage that are not considered in this study constitute the cause for 47% change in VCP. Meanwhile, the corresponding Likelihood Ratio (LR) statistic and Prob (LR statistic) values of 3.200452 and 0.073618 at 10% significant level signify that the model has performed well, thereby, making its estimations dependable. Looking at the relative statistics with the coefficient value of -502688 and Prob. value of 0.0301 which is less than 0.05 at 5% significant level, shows that SCI exert negative but significant influence on VCP within the period of study. This suggests strong influence of connectedness arising from the use of social media on the performance of venture capital.

4.3 Discussion of Findings

From the aid of PPML estimator, it is observed that social media coverage captured by social connectedness index significantly influence venture capital investments (measured by startup fund in fintech and venture capital performance). This implies that use of social media coverage to initiate awareness greatly determine the investment decisions of VC firms. This easily points to them the nature, size, as well as the location of startups enterprises to invest their equity fund.

However, its relationship is negative in both cases which negates the a priori expectations, thereby, contradicting the findings of Nguyen et al (2023); Wang et al (2023) with positive relationships. This negative relationship that portrays failure of startups despite the increase in SCI is in alignment with the report of Weetracker in collaboration with Gree Tec Capital Africa Foundation that Nigeria has a startup failure rate of 61.07% as at 2023 (Aribisala, 2023). Reasons for this contradiction and failures are not far-fetched as they could be

attributed to some of the challenges that are associated with startups such as fear of survival amidst highly established competitors, unstable economic situation, as well as insecurity which were common in the terrain of Nigeria within the period of study. Economic instability manifested in high exchange rate disparity, hyper-inflation, high cost of production and high tax-burden, have been the trend in Nigeria. More so, the social challenge of kidnapping, boko-haram insurgencies (Akpovogbeta&Motajo, 2020; Premium Times, 2023) as well as riotous agitations from diverse ethnic groups in the country for government presence and provisions, are enough to masquerade any potential venture capitalists in spite of the connectivity and awareness of their creativity and entrepreneurship created on the social media platform.

5. Concluding Remarks and Policy Recommendations

The study shows that social media coverage negatively but significantly determine venture capital investments in Nigeria. However, the presence of strong relationship between social media coverage and venture capital investments in this study, suggests that the concerned stakeholders (monetary authority and government) should create and sustain a conducive ambience that would guarantee economic stability and peaceful operations of startups' enterprises.

Contribution of this paper to the literature

As a contribution to knowledge, this paper unveils the prominence of social media coverage as a vital avenue for fruitful investment decisions by the venture capitalists especially in emerging economies.

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Appendix 1: Data on Employed Variables and Their Sources

Year	A	B	C	D	SCI	NSFIF
	Facebook Users in Nigeria In M	Facebook Users in US In M	A+B	A×B	[(A+B)/(A×B)] %	N' M
2015	11.06	132.9	143.96	1469.874	10	143.96
2016	11.17	189	200.17	2111.13	9	200.17
2017	11.23	236	247.23	2650.28	9	247.23
2018	14.1	241	255.1	3398.1	8	255.1
2019	18.47	244	262.47	4506.68	6	262.47
2020	23.88	256	279.88	6113.28	5	279.88
2021	29.64	267	296.64	7913.88	4	296.64
2022	36.24	264	300.24	9567.36	3	300.24

Sources:

- 1) SCI = Social Connectedness Index (for Nigeria & US), Authors' Computation
- 2) NSFIF = Nigeria Startup Funds in Fintech (Sasu, 2023, May 24th). Total value of fintech startup funding in Nigeria from 2015 to 2022 (Converted to naira, using the average official exchange rate in corresponding years).
- 3) FUN = Facebook Users in Nigeria (Sasu, 2023, September 6th).
- 4) FUUS = Facebook Users in US (Iqbal, 2024, January 8th).